

Caring for old migrants and old people from minorities groups

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A personal network on exchanging ideas and sharing experiences in intercultural elderly care

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ENVEJECIMIENTO ACTIVO - INTERCULTURALIDAD - DIVERSIDAD

<p>NUESTRA VISIÓN</p> <p>Ponemos en valor la diversidad y el respeto a la individualidad en el colectivo de personas mayores</p>	<p>QUÉ HACEMOS</p> <p>Identificamos oportunidades en una población mayor cada vez más heterogénea</p>
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A migrant can be defined as 'any person who is moving or has moved across an international border or within a State away from his or her habitual place of residence, regardless of (1) the person's legal status; (2) whether the movement is voluntary or involuntary; (3) what the causes for the movement are; or (4) what the length of the stay is' (International Organization for Migration [IOM], 2018).

- After WWII Europe needed foreign workers to rebuilt the continent.
- Spanish, Italians, Turkish, Moroccans, African-Caribbean people (Windrush)
- No integration policies

Old migrants in Europe

- Ageing of working migrants,
- Policies of reunification,
- Increased mobility of the elderly people
- Demographic change of people living longer*

* (Wilkins 2019).

Upcoming generation of older adults

- Phenomenon of ageing migrants is becoming increasingly common in the European Union (Ciobanu, Fokkema, and Nedelcu 2016).
 - Belgium around 32% migrant background 2018, and it is estimated that in 2021 50% of older population.
 - Sweden citizens born in a foreign country in 2018 was 18%
 - The Netherlands – in 2019 was 24%
- Very diverse population. Comes not only from traditional migration countries like Morocco, Turkey, or southern-Europe.
- Specific social and health risk factors

Old migrants in the UK

- An estimated 19% of the UK-born were at least 65 years old in 2019, compared to 11% of migrants. Among the foreign-born, there is a lot of variation depending on the place of origin. Only 1% of people born in Romania or Bulgaria were aged 65+ compared to 17% of those born in the EU-14.

Age distribution of the UK's foreign-born population, 2019

Source: Migration Observatory analysis of Annual Population Survey, 2019.

The older ethnic minority population (aged 50+) is expected to more than double between 2007 and 2026 from 1.7 million to 3.8 million. *

ONS describes any reason given other than work, join or study as 'going home to live'. In Figure ii we describe these as 'Other' and combine with non-specific responses and where no reason was given. ONS has confirmed these figures include asylum seekers but only those who identify as such when interviewed for their IPS survey. We assume that 'other' will include those whose reason is to retire in the UK and mainly covers returning UK nationals

Older migrants – how to care

“Although factors shaping aging processes are largely similar across populations, migrant-specific risk factors exist. These include exposure to

- health risks before and during migration;
- a more disadvantaged socioeconomic position;
- language barriers and low health literacy;
- cultural factors influencing health-seeking behaviours;
- and psychosocial vulnerability and discrimination affecting health and quality of life.”

(Kristiansen et al., 2016)

Upcoming generation of older adults – Superdiversity

Social health care actions

Community Engagement – Principle of solidarity

Empower the old immigrants

Increase **cultural sensitive care**

Respecting **diversity**

Recognition and appreciation.

The perspective of Human Rights inspires social and health workers to develop person-centered interventions and respect individuality. .

Neighbourhoods as ‘ideal’ places to organise care and social services

- Ageing in place ‘good’ for maintaining independence and levels of well-being
- Needs-based, close to clients and their networks
- Good fit with turn to ‘active citizenship’: **emphasis on neighbourhood inhabitants, not on minority groups.**

Reaching out to older migrants

- Organised cross-linkages between professionals: - neighbourhoods: regular meeting opportunities for professionals working in the neighbourhood -
- Ad-hoc linkages with neighbourhood teams: - recruiting new key figures ('sleutelfiguren') for (new) migrant groups - staff at day care centres, hospitals - personal assistants.

The Bristol Somali Resource Centre (BSRC)

The role of the care provider

- Interpreters often not used
- Growing awareness of role of health literacy
- Stereotypes
- This 'discourse of looking after their own' (Peckover and Chidlaw, 2007) has said to influence care providers who refrain from offering care services, leaving migrant elderly and their carers unsupported

Health care actions

**Promoting social inclusion
in housing with care and
support for older people in
England and Wales (DICE)**

- Local governments should put much more effort in monitoring agreements about cultural sensitivity with the care providers they contract. If they don't, too much pressure for reaching out to older migrants is placed on professionals with a migration background
- In order to reach out to older migrants who have not used long-term care and social services before, it is necessary to grant them easier access to care and social services

Health care actions

- Good care for elderly migrants is providing care responsive to their needs, even if that is in contrast with professional beliefs (eg about telling a diagnosis)
- Rather than gaining insight in cultural norms and values of patients we need to do more research about implicit bias and stereotyping of care providers
- Professional caregivers should be trained to recognize and respect the access-related abilities of older migrants and their informal carers

Key messages

- Older migrants form a small but important part of an ageing minority ethnic population in the UK. This community already **faces significant social inequalities and new arrivals may face additional challenges in integrating into life in the UK**. Older migrants of working age usually come to work. Older migrants above the retirement age usually come to join family.
- Many older migrants struggle particularly with **issues including poverty, isolation, information and access to services**. These may be similar to difficulties experienced by older UK nationals, but are exacerbated by a combination of unfamiliarity with the UK as well as a different cultural background.
- Older migrants may be at a **greater risk of poverty as they will not have the financial securities from long-term employment in the UK**.
- Older migrants may be **socially isolated due to unfamiliarity with their locality and services, as well as being reluctant to use public transport**. Getting information to them about local groups and services is an important starting point.*

*Integration up North (2015) Older migrants. Introduction to Migration series, Guidance booklet #14. Migration Yorkshire: Leeds.

Key messages

- There may be good **reasons why older migrants are not fluent in English**. Verbal information disseminated through trusted local networks can be an important supplement to providing translated written information.
- Improving health outcomes for older migrants can involve steps such as **providing information about illnesses that often develop in older age and building on older migrants' preferred coping strategies**.
- Older migrants may face additional or earlier health problems related to ageing faster UK-born older people.
- **Asking older migrants about their needs is a simple step that can lead to more culturally appropriate services**. Promoting accessibility does not necessarily involve translating services or changing a service but may require making services known to targeted user group.
- Older migrants provide significant contributions to local communities and the economy. For example, they provide financial support to their extended family or indirectly through unpaid childcare. *

*Integration up North (2015) Older migrants. Introduction to Migration series, Guidance booklet #14. Migration Yorkshire: Leeds.

Diversity may be the hardest thing
for a society to live with, and
perhaps the most dangerous thing
for a society to be without.

— *William Sloane Coffin Jr.* —

¡GRACIAS! THANK YOU!

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